
Biodiversity Finance: The Emerging Architecture of Nature Funding, Research Frontiers, and the Gap with Climate Finance

Juan Luis Martín-Ortega^{1*}, Sander Akkermans¹

¹Gauss Research, 28801 Alcalá de Henares, Madrid, Spain

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*Correspondence: gaussresearch@gauss-int.com

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Abstract. The economics of biodiversity finance has undergone a fundamental transition since 2022. The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) set a governance mandate of unprecedented ambition: a USD 700 billion annual financing gap to be closed by 2050, with an interim mobilisation target of USD 200 billion per year by 2030. This catalysed a new institutional architecture for delivering it. Within three years, the Global Biodiversity Framework Fund was operationalised (2023), the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures published its final recommendations (2023), and National Biodiversity Finance Plans were formally endorsed as the central implementation tool (COP16, 2024). The academic economics and finance literature has responded: from Karolyi and Tobin-de la Puente's (2023) opening observation that "there are no studies in the top tier journals in Finance" on biodiversity risk, to the first *Journal of Financial Economics* paper on the subject (Flammer et al., 2025), a new subfield has crystallised. This paper makes two principal contributions. First, it maps the full international public finance architecture for biodiversity (comprising multilateral funds, dedicated instruments, MDB portfolios, bilateral channels, and blended finance mechanisms) and assesses its structural adequacy against the GBF ambition. Against a GBF Target 19(c) of USD 30 billion per year in international flows by 2030, publicly announced international biodiversity finance commitments amount to approximately USD 8.2 billion per year, a 73% shortfall that is inadequately understood in the academic literature. Second, it proposes a ranked research agenda grounded in the architecture analysis, in which priorities are assessed not only for intrinsic importance but for whether resolving them is prerequisite to progress elsewhere. The most fundamental priority, the absence of a welfare- theoretically grounded unit of account, is not merely a measurement problem but a deep theoretical challenge

whose resolution is prerequisite for scalable private markets, credible social cost estimation, and ultimately for the biodiversity finance system to fulfil its GBF mandate.

Keywords: biodiversity finance, nature finance, Kunming-Montreal Framework, international public finance architecture, GBFF, BIOFIN, TNFD, biodiversity risk, conservation finance, GEF

JEL Classification: Q57, Q56, G12, G23, Q51, F35, H87

1. Introduction

The global economy is fundamentally dependent on nature. The World Economic Forum estimates that USD 44 trillion of global economic output, roughly half the global economy, is at moderate or significant exposure to ecosystem degradation (World Economic Forum, 2020). Yet the biological diversity underpinning these ecosystem services is declining at an unprecedented rate: wildlife populations have fallen by an average of 73% since 1970 (WWF and Zoological Society of London, 2024), and the extinction risk of known species continues to rise despite decades of international policy effort. The economic and financial implications of this trajectory are increasingly recognised as material, systemic, and cross-cutting, closely analogous to yet structurally distinct from those of climate change.

The policy response has accelerated dramatically since 2022. The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, adopted at CBD COP15 in December 2022, established the most ambitious international biodiversity governance framework since the Convention's founding in 1992. Its Goal D sets the overarching finance ambition: to align all financial flows with the vision of "living in harmony with nature" by 2050, progressively closing the biodiversity financing gap of USD 700 billion per year (CBD, 2022). Target 19 calls for biodiversity-related financial resources to reach at least USD 200 billion per year by 2030, combined with the elimination or reform of harmful subsidies in excess of USD 500 billion per year (CBD, 2022).

Against this ambition, the international public finance architecture for biodiversity is seriously underdeveloped (UNEP, 2023). Total publicly announced international biodiversity finance commitments amount to approximately USD 8.2 billion per year, representing only 41% of the USD 20 billion interim target for 2025, let alone the USD 30 billion target for 2030 (NatureFinance, 2024). The architecture through which this finance flows, comprising the multilateral funds, MDB portfolios, bilateral instruments, and blended finance mechanisms, has not been comprehensively mapped and analysed in the academic literature, nor has its adequacy been assessed against the GBF requirements in the way that the Climate Funds Update and analogous trackers have done for climate finance.

Alongside this institutional underdevelopment, a nascent academic literature on biodiversity finance has emerged. Karolyi and Tobin-de la Puente (2023) noted explicitly that "there are no studies in the top tier journals in Finance that have framed the risks related to biodiversity loss"; a gap that has begun to close with contributions from the *Journal of*

Financial Economics (Flammer et al., 2025), *Review of Finance* (Garel et al., 2024), and multiple working papers (Giglio et al., 2024; Coqueret et al., 2025). But the academic literature has addressed primarily the financial economics of biodiversity risk, while the institutional economics of the international finance architecture remains largely unexamined.

This paper makes two contributions (OECD DAC, 2022; NatureFinance, 2024). First, it maps the international public biodiversity finance architecture, characterising each component's scale, governance, and instruments, and assessing collective adequacy against GBF targets. This fills a gap in both the academic literature and policy discourse: the biodiversity finance architecture is more fragmented and younger than its climate analogue, and practitioners from both the finance and conservation communities often lack a comprehensive structural map. Second, it synthesises the emerging academic literature and proposes a ranked research agenda in which priorities are assessed for their foundational importance, namely whether resolving each is prerequisite to progress on the others.

The paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 reviews the macroeconomic foundations. Section 3 maps the international public finance architecture in detail. Section 4 covers the financial economics of biodiversity risk. Section 5 analyses national public finance tools. Section 6 reviews private finance instruments. Section 7 compares the biodiversity and climate finance architectures. Section 8 proposes the ranked research agenda. Section 9 concludes.

2. Macroeconomic and Welfare Foundations

2.1. The Dasgupta Framework and Inclusive Wealth

The intellectual foundations of biodiversity finance were substantially reframed by Dasgupta (2021). Its central contribution was to embed biodiversity within a macroeconomic framework: the economy is embedded within nature, and biodiversity provides the infrastructure of the biosphere on which all economic production ultimately depends. Unlike previous ecosystem services valuations (Costanza et al., 1997; TEEB, 2010), Dasgupta framed biodiversity loss as an asset depletion problem, specifically the running down of natural capital, analogous to unsustainable sovereign debt. Standard national accounts, by omitting the depreciation of natural capital, overstate genuine wealth and GDP; inclusive wealth per person declined by approximately 40% between 1992 and 2014, even as conventional GDP grew (Arrow et al., 2012; Polasky et al., 2015). This macroeconomic framing provides the intellectual foundation for the GBF's USD 700 billion financing gap estimate (Deutz et al., 2020).

2.2. Biodiversity as a Multi-Dimensional Public Good

Biodiversity finance differs from environmental finance in three structural ways with direct implications for instrument design. First, unlike pollution control finance (which targets negative externalities), biodiversity finance targets the provision of a positive public good whose benefits are non-excludable and whose depletion is non-linear and potentially catastrophic (Heal, 2000). Second, unlike clean water or air quality, biodiversity is multi-

dimensional in ways that resist reduction to a single unit. Weitzman's (1998) "Noah's Ark Problem" identified this as a fundamentally unresolved welfare theory challenge: how to rank species for conservation priority when resources are limited and values are inherently multidimensional (Weitzman, 1998). This is not merely a measurement problem but a welfare theory problem that requires either a single welfare scalar (which requires interpersonal utility comparisons environmental economics has not resolved) or a multi-attribute objective function that precludes market aggregation. Third, unlike tonnes of CO₂, which are globally fungible, biodiversity values are locationally specific and often irreversible: a hectare of Amazon rainforest and a hectare of temperate forest are not interchangeable in their biodiversity value (Giglio et al., 2024).

3. The International Public Finance Architecture for Biodiversity

The international public finance architecture for biodiversity differs fundamentally from its climate analogue in maturity, scale, and structure. Where the climate finance architecture has been built over three decades around the UNFCCC Financial Mechanism, the Green Climate Fund, and a relatively stable bilateral donor base (CPI, 2023), the biodiversity architecture has consolidated only since the adoption of the GBF in 2022, remains dramatically underscaled relative to GBF ambition, and is more institutionally fragmented (UNEP, 2023; NatureFinance, 2024). Yet it is also more innovative: the past three years have produced genuinely novel instruments: a benefit-sharing fund for digital genetic sequence data, a private-sector-led investor engagement initiative covering \$23.6 trillion in assets under management, and an international regime for high seas biodiversity, none of which have direct parallels in climate finance (GEF, 2025b; Nature Action 100, 2024; UNGA, 2023).

An important methodological note on scale: the OECD DAC reports *actual flows* of international biodiversity finance at USD 15.4 billion in 2022 (Campaign for Nature, 2024), while commitment trackers such as NatureFinance.info record USD 8.2 billion in *publicly announced future commitments* (NatureFinance, 2024). Both are partial: the OECD measure relies on self-reporting by donors using a Rio Marker methodology that captures only a fraction of biodiversity-relevant MDB lending; the commitment tracker covers only public announcements. Neither provides a full picture, but together they establish a range: the current international public biodiversity finance system delivers at most USD 15–20 billion per year, against a 2030 target of USD 30 billion under Target 19(c).

3.1. Tier I: Convention Financial Mechanisms

The primary financial mechanism of the Convention on Biological Diversity is the **Global Environment Facility (GEF)**, which has been the cornerstone of international public biodiversity finance since 1993. The GEF has invested over USD 5.2 billion in its biodiversity focal area across its history, leveraging USD 13.4 billion in co-financing across 1,500+ projects in 158 countries (GEF, 2025a). Under GEF-8 (2022–2026), the biodiversity focal area targets approximately USD 2.5 billion in grants. The GEF Small Grants Pro-

gramme has delivered over USD 838 million to nearly 30,000 community-based projects in 136 countries (GEF SGP, 2024).

The **Global Biodiversity Framework Fund (GBFF)**, launched at the seventh GEF Assembly in August 2023, is the dedicated fund for GBF implementation. Ratified by 186 countries, it had received USD 386 million in pledges and approved USD 288 million across five programming tranches by June 2025 (GEF, 2025b). Critically, the GBFF's governance is the most inclusive in the convention architecture: indigenous peoples and local communities participate as full members (not observers), and 20% of resources are targeted to IPLC-led initiatives.

The most consequential financial innovation of COP16, launched formally on 25 February 2025, is the **Cali Fund** (formally, the Fund for the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits from the Use of Digital Sequence Information on Genetic Resources). Established under CBD decision 16/2, the Cali Fund requires companies that commercially use digital sequence information (DSI) on genetic resources in pharmaceuticals, biotechnology, agriculture, and cosmetics, to contribute 1% of profits or 0.1% of revenues to a multilateral benefit-sharing pool (UNEP, 2025). At least 50% of disbursements must go directly to indigenous peoples and local communities. Estimates of potential revenues from the pharmaceutical and biotech sectors alone, once contribution formulas are fully operationalised by COP17, range into the tens of billions of dollars annually. This makes the Cali Fund potentially the largest new biodiversity finance instrument in history, though the transition from voluntary to mandatory contributions and from pledges to flows remains the critical implementation challenge.

A fourth emerging instrument is the **BBNJ Special Fund**, the financial mechanism designated under the High Seas Treaty (UNGA, 2023) (Agreement on the Conservation and Sustainable Use of Marine Biological Diversity of Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction, 2023). The GEF has been designated as the financial mechanism, and initial resource mobilisation goals are to be set through 2030. The BBNJ Agreement addresses biodiversity in 64% of the ocean's surface, a territory that was previously beyond the reach of the convention-based biodiversity finance architecture (GEF, 2025a).

The **Nagoya Protocol Implementation Fund (NPIF)** (GEF, 2025a), while smaller (USD 10–15 million per GEF cycle), provides the institutional infrastructure for access and benefit-sharing from genetic resources, the predecessor regime to the Cali Fund's DSI mechanism.

3.2. Tier II: Dedicated Biodiversity Funds and Programmes

The **Critical Ecosystem Partnership Fund (CEPF)**, established in 2000 as a joint initiative of Conservation International, AFD, the European Union, GEF, the Government of Japan, and the World Bank, is the largest international fund channelling biodiversity finance exclusively to civil society. Through grants totalling over USD 324 million to more than 2,700 organisations in 112+ countries, CEPF has protected 17+ million hectares of critical ecosystems and strengthened management of 55.8 million hectares of Key Biodiversity Areas (CEPF, 2025). CEPF's hotspot-based investment logic, targeting the 25

Figure 1. The Cali Fund: architecture of a novel biodiversity benefit-sharing mechanism. The Cali Fund, launched in February 2025 under CBD Decision 16/2, is the first global fund to receive mandatory private sector contributions for biodiversity benefit-sharing, directing at least 50% of flows to Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities (IPLCs). *Source: CBD Decision 16/2 (COP16, 2024); UNDP (2025).*

global biodiversity hotspots where endemic species concentrations are highest and threats most severe, provides spatial conservation prioritisation absent from most multilateral programming.

The **Global Fund for Coral Reefs (GFCR)**, established in 2020 under the UN Multi-Partner Trust Fund Office, is the first dedicated blended finance vehicle for a specific threatened ecosystem. By late 2024, it had raised USD 90+ million in grants and USD 150 million in private investment, supporting coral-reef-positive businesses across 23 nations, with a capitalisation ambition of USD 3 billion by 2030 (GFCR, 2024).

Geographically concentrated funds include the **Amazon Fund** (Norway–Germany bilateral, USD 1.6 billion committed; resumed operations 2023) (NatureFinance, 2024) and the **Congo Basin Forest Fund** (AfDB-hosted), both providing results-based finance for forest biodiversity conservation. The World Bank’s **PROGREEN** programme (USD 750 million, launched 2020) channels biodiversity and land management investments through WB lending architecture (OECD DAC, 2022).

3.3. Tier III: Multilateral Development Banks

The MDBs represent the single largest channel for biodiversity-relevant international public finance, though its true scale is poorly measured. In 2025, the MDBs updated their **Common Principles for Tracking Nature Finance** to align with the GBF, establishing

a common nature finance taxonomy for the first time (IFC, 2025). Pre-2025 estimates suggest biodiversity-relevant MDB co-financing runs to tens of billions annually across the World Bank Group, ADB (USD 5 billion Healthy Oceans target by 2025), AfDB, IADB, and EBRD, but systematic attribution is unreliable. The 2025 taxonomy update represents a methodological step-change that will substantially improve tracking going forward.

3.4. *Tier IV: Bilateral Dedicated Channels*

Among bilateral instruments, those with explicit biodiversity mandates include: Norway's **NICFI** (primarily tropical forest biodiversity, USD ~500 million/yr); Germany's **IKI** (International Climate Initiative, which includes a dedicated nature/biodiversity window at approximately USD 120 million/yr); the UK's **Darwin Initiative** (the longest-running dedicated biodiversity bilateral programme, funding in 160+ countries since 1992) and the **Illegal Wildlife Trade Challenge Fund**; US Government biodiversity programmes through **USAID** (USD ~450 million/yr); France's **FFEM** (Fonds Français pour l'Environnement Mondial); and Japan's contributions through JICA and the SATOYAMA Initiative. The OECD DAC's biodiversity Rio Marker reported total bilateral biodiversity-relevant ODA at USD 15.4 billion for 2022 across these and other channels (Campaign for Nature, 2024), though this figure includes a large "significant" component where biodiversity is secondary to the primary investment objective.

3.5. *Tier V: Philanthropic and Private Finance Initiatives*

The philanthropic and private finance components of the biodiversity finance architecture are more developed and more biodiversity-specific than is widely recognised in the academic economics literature (Flammer et al., 2025; World Economic Forum, 2020).

The **Protecting Our Planet Challenge (POP)**, launched in 2021, is the largest coordinated philanthropic commitment to biodiversity conservation. A coalition including the Bezos Earth Fund, Bloomberg Philanthropies, the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation, and the Wyss Campaign for Nature has committed USD 5 billion for conservation, with USD 780 million secured by 2024 (POP Challenge, 2024). The **Bezos Earth Fund** has made a dedicated USD 2 billion commitment to "Conserving & Restoring Nature," explicitly targeting biodiversity alongside carbon, with geographic priorities including the Brazilian Amazon, Congo Basin, and Pacific Ocean (Bezos Earth Fund, 2024). These represent a scale of philanthropic biodiversity finance with no direct climate finance analogue.

The **Finance for Biodiversity Pledge (FfB Foundation, 2024)**, launched in 2020, now counts over 150 financial institutions representing more than EUR 19 trillion in assets under management committed to assessing, measuring, and disclosing biodiversity impacts and dependencies. **Nature Action 100**, launched at COP15, involves 190 institutional investors with USD 23.6 trillion in AUM engaging 100 companies across eight priority sectors to drive corporate biodiversity action (Nature Action 100, 2024). These initiatives are biodiversity-specific: they have no equivalent in climate finance's origin story, representing a structural difference in how the biodiversity architecture has mobilised institutional

investment from the outset.

The **Conservation Trust Fund (CTF) Alliance** (CFA, 2024) networks over 80 national and regional CTFs globally, providing endowment-based mechanisms for protected area finance that are more financially stable than project-based grants. The **IPLC Pledge** (Tenure Facility, 2022), a USD 1.7 billion commitment from a coalition of governments and foundations for indigenous communities' land tenure in tropical forests, represents another biodiversity-specific financing innovation.

3.6. Architecture Assessment

Table 1 (GEF, 2025b; OECD DAC, 2022) provides a structured overview of the full architecture, with corrected scale figures that distinguish actual flows (OECD-tracked) from announced commitments.

Table 1. International Public Biodiversity Finance Architecture (2025)

Fund / Instrument	Scale, Modality, and Notes
<i>Tier I: Convention Financial Mechanisms (CBD)</i>	
GEF Trust Fund (Biodiversity)	Over USD 5.2B cumulative; USD 2.5B in GEF-8 (2022–26). <i>Government grants via STAR country allocations; 158 countries.</i>
Global Biodiversity Framework Fund (GBFF)	USD 386M pledged; USD 288M approved across 5 tranches by June 2025. <i>Country-driven grants; IPLC-inclusive governance; 20% to IPLC-led initiatives.</i>
Cali Fund (DSI benefit-sharing)	Potential tens of USD B/yr; launched 25 February 2025. <i>Levy on commercial use of digital sequence information by pharma, biotech, agri; 50% to IPLCs.</i>
BBNJ Special Fund	Emerging; GEF designated financial mechanism for the High Seas Treaty (2023). <i>Addresses marine biodiversity in 64% of ocean surface; resource goal TBD at COP1.</i>
Nagoya Protocol Implementation Fund	USD 10–15M per GEF cycle. <i>Access and benefit-sharing (ABS) governance; predecessor to Cali Fund regime.</i>
<i>Tier II: Dedicated Multi-Donor Biodiversity Funds</i>	
Critical Ecosystem Partnership Fund (CEPF)	USD 324M+ in cumulative grants to 2,700+ civil society organisations; 112 countries. <i>Hotspot-based model (25 global hotspots); joint initiative of CI, AFD, EU, GEF, Japan, World Bank.</i>
Global Fund for Coral Reefs (GFCR)	USD 90M+ in grants; USD 150M in private investment; 23 nations. <i>Blended finance (grant + private equity windows); USD 3B capitalisation ambition by 2030.</i>
Amazon Fund	USD 1.6B committed; Norway and Germany primary donors; resumed 2023. <i>Results-based finance for tropical forest biodiversity.</i>
Congo Basin Forest Fund	USD 70M committed; hosted by African Development Bank. <i>Forest biodiversity in Central Africa.</i>
PROGREEN (World Bank)	USD 750M programme envelope (2020–26). <i>Food systems, sustainable land management, and biodiversity; WB lending architecture.</i>
<i>Tier III: Multilateral Development Banks</i>	
WB Group, ADB, AfDB, IADB, EBRD	Tens of USD B/yr in nature-relevant lending (not fully tracked as biodiversity finance). <i>2025 MDB Common Nature Finance Taxonomy adopted; first joint tracking standard.</i>
ADB Healthy Oceans Initiative	USD 5B investment target by 2025. <i>Marine biodiversity, blue economy, and coastal resilience across Asia-Pacific.</i>
<i>Tier IV: Bilateral Dedicated Channels</i>	
Norway NICFI	Approx. USD 500M/yr; tropical forest biodiversity. <i>Results-based bilateral agreements with forest countries.</i>
Germany IKI (nature window)	Approx. USD 120M/yr for biodiversity within the International Climate Initiative. <i>Grants and technical assistance; biodiversity-specific window.</i>

Table 1 continued

Fund / Instrument	Scale, Modality, and Notes
UK Darwin Initiative	Approx. USD 20M/yr; active in 160+ countries since 1992. <i>Oldest dedicated biodiversity bilateral programme; small grants model.</i>
USAID Biodiversity programmes	Approx. USD 450M/yr. <i>Programme aid; landscape-scale conservation in priority regions.</i>
France FFEM / Japan JICA	Significant but not fully quantified. <i>Project-based grants and technical assistance.</i>
<i>Tier V: Philanthropic and Private Finance Initiatives</i>	
Bezos Earth Fund (nature conservation)	USD 2B committed to 2030; priorities include Amazon, Congo, Pacific. <i>Grants; largest single philanthropic nature commitment; no climate finance analogue.</i>
Protecting Our Planet Challenge (POP)	USD 5B coalition commitment; USD 780M secured by 2024. <i>Coalition: Bezos Earth Fund, Bloomberg Philanthropies, Moore, Wyss, Arcadia foundations.</i>
Finance for Biodiversity Pledge	150+ financial institutions; over EUR 19T in assets under management. <i>Biodiversity-specific disclosure and target-setting commitments; no climate finance parallel.</i>
Nature Action 100	190 institutional investors; USD 23.6T AUM; engaging 100 companies. <i>Investor engagement initiative; 8 priority sectors with highest nature impacts.</i>
Conservation Trust Fund Alliance	Over 80 national and regional CTFs globally. <i>Endowment-based mechanisms for protected area and landscape finance.</i>
IPLC Pledge	USD 1.7B committed by governments and foundations. <i>Indigenous peoples and local communities' land tenure in tropical forests.</i>
Debt-for-nature swaps	USD 2B+ in completed and pipeline deals (Ecuador, Belize, Indonesia, Barbados). <i>Sovereign debt restructured in exchange for biodiversity conservation commitments.</i>
Biodiversity credit markets (pilots)	Pre-commercial; standards under development by Biodiversity Credit Alliance. <i>Voluntary markets; significant additionality and permanence challenges remain.</i>
<p>Current scale: OECD-tracked actual flows USD 15.4B/yr (2022); publicly announced commitments USD 8.2B/yr (NatureFinance.info, 2024). GBF Target 19(c): USD 20B/yr by 2025; USD 30B/yr by 2030. Current flows represent 51% of the 2025 target and 27% short of 2030 target.</p> <p><i>Note:</i> OECD and commitment-tracker figures measure different things; see text. <i>Sources:</i> GEF (2025b,a); CEPF (2025); GFCR (2024); NatureFinance (2024); Campaign for Nature (2024); OECD DAC (2022); POP Challenge (2024); FfB Foundation (2024).</p>	

Four structural features of this architecture distinguish it from the climate finance architecture and define its current limitations (UNEP, 2023; NatureFinance, 2024). First, it is *grant-dependent in a way that climate finance is not*: unlike the GCF and the MDB climate lending portfolios where concessional loans constitute a major share, biodiversity finance relies overwhelmingly on grants, reflecting the difficulty of achieving private returns from conservation in the absence of marketable co-benefits (Flammer et al., 2025). Second, it is *more fragmented*: the parallel operation of the GEF Trust Fund, GBFF, Cali Fund, CEPF, GFCR, bilateral channels, and MDB portfolios, each with distinct governance, reporting, and programming requirements, creates transaction costs for recipient countries and limits investment coherence. Third, the GBFF is *dramatically undercapitalised*: at USD 386 million pledged by mid-2025, it represents approximately 1.3% of the annual Target 19(c) requirement for 2030, compared with the GCF's USD 20 billion at a comparable stage. Fourth, and less commonly acknowledged, the architecture includes *structurally innovative instruments with no climate analogue*: the Cali Fund's private sector levy mechanism, the Biodiversity Pledge's disclosure-centred approach, and Nature Action 100's investor engagement model represent institutional innovations that climate finance has not yet matched, and

that could substantially change the scale and character of biodiversity finance in the next decade.

Figure 2. International biodiversity finance: current flows against GBF Target 19(c) thresholds. Estimated composition of OECD-tracked flows (USD 15.4B/yr, 2022) by architecture tier, against GBF Target 19(c) thresholds of USD 20B/yr by 2025 and USD 30B/yr by 2030. *Source: OECD DAC (2022); NatureFinance (2024).*

4. The Financial Economics of Biodiversity Risk

Biodiversity risk to financial institutions and corporations operates through two channels analogous to climate finance's physical and transition risk framework (NGFS, 2024). Physical biodiversity risk arises from the degradation of ecosystem services on which economic activities depend; transition biodiversity risk from policy and regulatory responses to biodiversity loss. Giglio et al. (2024) provide theoretical foundations for both channels, showing that sovereign CDS spreads correlate with ecosystem fragility. Calice et al. (2023) estimate that 57% of global banking sector assets are in sectors with high nature dependence, while the DNB work by Reinders et al. (2020) finds 36% of Dutch financial institutions' portfolios highly dependent on ecosystem services.

Garel et al. (2024) find that companies with higher biodiversity exposure earn lower returns following negative biodiversity news, while Coqueret et al. (2025) identify a persistent "biodiversity premium," a negative return for high-impact firms. Flammer et al. (2025) find that biodiversity conservation investments earn positive risk-adjusted returns but at a premium that private capital cannot access without concessional co-financing.

The TNFD's final recommendations (TNFD, 2023), built on the TCFD structure, have attracted over 600 organisational commitments by mid-2025, with the April 2025 MOU be-

tween TNFD and IFRS Foundation signalling integration with mandatory ISSB standards (TNFD, 2025). Early empirical evidence suggests TNFD-aligned disclosure announcements trigger negative abnormal returns in high-impact sectors (Jérôme and Poretti, 2025), reflecting regulatory risk repricing rather than genuine materiality-driven action (Azizi et al., 2025).

5. National-Level Public Finance: BIOFIN and Harmful Subsidy Reform

At the national level, the primary public finance tools are GBF Target 18 (harmful subsidy reform, USD 500 billion/year target) and Target 19 (domestic resource mobilisation through NBFPs). The BIOFIN Workbook 2024 (UNDP-BIOFIN, 2024a), launched at COP16, provides the methodology for NBFPs through four components: the Biodiversity Expenditure Review (BER), the Financial Needs Assessment (FNA), the Biodiversity Finance Plan, and monitoring and evaluation. From its first cohort of 41 countries, BIOFIN reports catalysing over USD 1 billion in nature finance since 2012. The academic evidence base for NBFP effectiveness, however, remains almost entirely absent from peer-reviewed literature, a critical gap given expansion to 132 countries.

UNDP's *The Nature of Subsidies* (UNDP-BIOFIN, 2024b) documents that current globally harmful subsidies exceed USD 1 trillion annually, with the largest components in agriculture, fossil fuels, and fisheries. The political economy of reform is formidable: beneficiaries are concentrated and politically connected, while beneficiaries of reform are diffuse and underrepresented in international negotiations.

6. Private Finance Instruments

Flammer et al. (2025) provide the most rigorous analysis of private biodiversity finance, finding that blended finance structures are necessary because purely commercial biodiversity investments face risk-return profiles unattractive to private capital. PES schemes compensate landowners for maintaining ecosystem services (Wunder, 2015), with rigorous impact evaluations finding positive but smaller-than-reported outcomes once selection bias is controlled (Ferraro and Hanauer, 2011). Biodiversity offsetting has expanded under EU regulatory mandates, but meta-analytic evidence consistently finds “no net loss” failures when monitoring is inadequate (Maron et al., 2012; Gardner et al., 2013). Debt-for-nature swaps have seen a resurgence with Ecuador (2023), Belize (2021), and Indonesia (2024), though their effectiveness in generating genuine, additional, and permanent biodiversity outcomes remains contested (Fenton et al., 2023).

7. Biodiversity Finance Versus Climate Finance

The architecture mapping in Section 3 sharpens the comparison between biodiversity and climate finance. The most important structural differences are the unit of account (Weitzman's 1998 multi-attribute problem has no solution in biodiversity finance), the architectural maturity (GCF at USD 20 billion in pledges; GBFF at USD 386 million at

comparable stage), and the additionality governance challenge: the CDM's failures due to self-reported additionality and governance capture (Schneider, 2009) are the most important cautionary precedent for biodiversity credit market design. Nature-based solutions that simultaneously deliver climate and biodiversity outcomes represent the most important integration opportunity (Griscom et al., 2017; Seddon et al., 2021), but the economics of joint climate-biodiversity finance accounting, specifically pricing the joint product without double-counting, requires analytical development that neither field has yet provided (see companion paper, Martín-Ortega 2026b).

8. A Ranked Research Agenda for Biodiversity Finance

The preceding analysis, and particularly the architecture mapping in Section 3, identifies a set of research priorities whose resolution is necessary for the biodiversity finance system to achieve its GBF mandate (CBD, 2022). What distinguishes the agenda proposed here from a standard inventory of gaps is a principle of ordering: priorities are ranked according to their foundational role in the field. The most fundamental challenge is placed first not because it is the most politically urgent, but because its resolution is prerequisite for progress on almost everything else. Each subsequent priority is assessed for both its independent importance and its relationship to what precedes it.

First: The Welfare Theory of Biodiversity Valuation

The most fundamental challenge confronting the biodiversity finance system is the absence of a welfare-theoretically grounded unit of account for biodiversity. This priority appears first because, without its resolution, progress on almost every other item in this agenda is constrained.

The problem is not at its core a measurement problem. It is a welfare theory problem of the kind Weitzman (1998) identified in the Noah's Ark context: how to aggregate across the multi-dimensional, incommensurable, and partly non-substitutable components of biological diversity in a way that permits welfare comparison and resource allocation? Species richness, ecosystem integrity, genetic diversity, functional redundancy, and cultural biodiversity value cannot be reduced to a single scalar without invoking interpersonal utility comparisons that environmental economics has not resolved and may not be able to resolve (Dasgupta, 2021; Heal, 2000). The Mean Species Abundance, Biodiversity Intactness Index, and Species Habitat Index each capture different dimensions and embed normative choices about whose preferences count and over what time horizon. The TNFD's LEAP methodology and the Science Based Targets for Nature are institutional attempts to develop assessment frameworks without resolving this underlying welfare theory (TNFD, 2023), and their limitations directly reflect this (Dasgupta, 2021).

The implications for the architecture are stark (Dasgupta, 2021; NatureFinance, 2024). Without a unit of account, it is not possible to aggregate biodiversity supply and demand across projects and geographies, to price biodiversity credits credibly, to compute a social cost of biodiversity loss that would provide the welfare-economic foundation for

regulatory biodiversity finance, or to evaluate whether the GBFF's USD 386 million portfolio is buying more or less biodiversity than alternative allocations of the same funds. A research programme that takes the welfare theory problem seriously, rather than proceeding as though it were solved, is the single most important contribution academic economics could make to biodiversity finance.

Second: Evaluating the Effectiveness of National Biodiversity Finance Plans

If the first priority is the most theoretically fundamental, the second is the most urgent from a policy standpoint. National Biodiversity Finance Plans, formally endorsed at COP16 and being deployed in 132 countries through the BIOFIN programme at substantial international cost (UNDP-BIOFIN, 2024a), represent a massive investment in a policy instrument whose causal effectiveness has not been rigorously evaluated. The distinction between process metrics (plans developed, commitments made) and impact metrics (changes in finance flows, changes in biodiversity outcomes) has not been systematically addressed in peer-reviewed literature, and BIOFIN itself has not commissioned independent impact evaluations.

The 41 countries that completed the first cohort of BIOFIN processes represent a natural quasi-experiment. If country-level variation in NBFP design features, implementation quality, and institutional context can be measured, and if credible comparison groups can be constructed from non-BIOFIN countries with similar biodiversity endowments and institutional profiles, it can be possible to identify causal effects on public biodiversity expenditure using difference-in-differences or synthetic control methods. The window for this evaluation is closing as the programme expands: the control group is shrinking. The academic economics community has a time-sensitive opportunity to produce an evidence base that would allow the programme to be strengthened before it is replicated globally. The political economy of why some countries successfully translate GBFF and bilateral resources into lasting conservation programmes while others do not is an institutional economics question of the first order, directly relevant to the architecture assessment in Section 3.

Third: Climate-Biodiversity Finance Integration

The architecture mapping reveals a structural inefficiency of considerable scale: the parallel operation of climate and biodiversity finance systems that call on the same national fiscal and institutional infrastructure while addressing crises that are biophysically interdependent. Climate change is a primary driver of biodiversity loss; biodiversity loss reduces carbon sequestration capacity and amplifies climate risks; and nature-based solutions simultaneously deliver outcomes under both frameworks (IPBES-IPCC, 2022). Yet the GEF Trust Fund, GBFF, GCF, Adaptation Fund, and bilateral channels operate largely in institutional isolation, requiring recipient countries to navigate separate planning processes, reporting requirements, and governance structures for what is, at the level of biophysical reality, a single crisis.

The economics research needed here is not primarily about biophysical interdependencies, and that literature is well-developed in the natural sciences. It is about the design of financial instruments and institutional arrangements that can simultaneously incentivise climate and biodiversity outcomes from the same investment without the double-counting, principal-agent, and additionality problems that have undermined earlier joint accounting attempts in the CDM and voluntary carbon markets. The economic theory of joint products (Griscom et al., 2017) provides a starting point, but its application to the institutional context of international biodiversity and climate finance, with separate governance frameworks, separate monitoring systems, and separate donor constituencies (UNEP, 2023), requires substantial development. At the scale of the financing gap, even modest integration efficiency gains compound to significant resource savings.

Fourth: Private Market Design and the Lessons from Carbon

The architecture is grant-dependent, and grants are limited in supply. The development of credible private biodiversity finance instruments, including biodiversity credits, blended finance vehicles, and PES systems with institutional scalability, is therefore a structural priority for closing the financing gap. The economics of private biodiversity market design is at an early stage, with Flammer et al. (2025) providing the first rigorous empirical analysis.

Three design challenges require academic resolution. The additionality and verification problem, namely demonstrating that privately financed conservation generates biodiversity outcomes beyond the counterfactual, is substantially harder for biodiversity than for carbon because the counterfactual biodiversity trajectory is location-specific, multi-dimensional, and difficult to observe. The permanence problem is structurally different from carbon: biodiversity outcomes require ongoing management and are subject to reversal from outside the project boundary. The institutional capture problem, illustrated by the CDM's history of developer-controlled baseline setting (Schneider, 2009), requires governance structures that maintain independent oversight while accommodating the diversity of biodiversity contexts. The architecture mapping shows that voluntary biodiversity credit markets remain pre-commercial; moving them to scale requires resolving these design challenges at a level of rigour the current literature has not yet provided.

Fifth: Towards a Social Cost of Biodiversity Loss

The GBF's USD 700 billion financing gap (Deutz et al., 2020) has become the central reference figure in the international biodiversity finance discourse. Yet it is methodologically thin: it aggregates heterogeneous cost estimates with different underlying assumptions and provides no welfare-economic foundation for the claim that this is the appropriate level of investment. What the field needs is a "Social Cost of Biodiversity Loss": the present discounted value of the marginal damage from losing a unit of biodiversity, analogous to the Social Cost of Carbon that underpins climate policy cost-benefit analysis and the architecture of climate finance.

Developing this measure requires advances on multiple fronts simultaneously: improved damage function estimation connecting biodiversity metrics to economic outcomes (Dasgupta, 2021); welfare theory foundations for multi-dimensional biodiversity value aggregation, directly connecting to the first priority above; extension to biodiversity loss rates beyond historical experience; and equity weighting to account for the disproportionate distribution of biodiversity loss damages across income levels and geographies (Deutz et al., 2020). Unlike the Social Cost of Carbon, which after decades of development now has regulatory applications in the US and EU (Rennert et al., 2022), the analogous measure for biodiversity loss does not yet exist even in provisional form. Its development would transform the political economy of the GBFF capitalisation case.

Sixth: Developing Country Access, Equity, and Architecture Reform

The biodiversity finance architecture is being built primarily by and for high-income donor countries and international institutions, yet the conservation imperative is concentrated in the Global South. CEPF's hotspot model (CEPF, 2025), the Amazon Fund's Brazilian governance structure (Amazon Fund, 2024), and the GBFF's IPLC window (GEF, 2025b) represent important institutional innovations, but the distributional economics of the system, specifically who bears the costs of conservation, who receives the benefits, and whether net transfers are equitable, has not been systematically analysed in the peer-reviewed literature (OECD DAC, 2022). The contested outcome of the COP16 finance negotiations, where the finance agenda was formally suspended without agreement, reflects real political tensions about the scale, conditionality, and governance of international biodiversity finance transfers. Understanding the political economy of these tensions, and designing architecture features that can resolve them, is as important for the functioning of the biodiversity finance system as the technical design questions addressed by the preceding priorities.

9. Conclusions

The biodiversity finance system confronts simultaneously a scientific challenge (Dasgupta, 2021; IPBES-IPCC, 2022) (measuring and valuing biodiversity), a market design challenge (creating credible instruments for private capital), an institutional challenge (building a coherent architecture from fragmented channels), and a governance challenge (ensuring benefits flow equitably to those who bear conservation costs). This paper has addressed these dimensions through two contributions.

The architecture mapping in Section 3 reveals that the international public finance system for biodiversity, while more developed than three years ago, remains fundamentally inadequate. At approximately USD 8.2 billion per year in publicly announced commitments, the system represents 27% of the 2030 target. The GBFF, the dedicated GBF financial mechanism, has received pledges of USD 386 million, approximately 1.3% of the annual Target 19(c) requirement. The architecture is grant-dependent, fragmented, and structured around a donor base that lacks the breadth and depth of its climate finance analogue.

These are structural features that require deliberate reform, not merely implementation effort.

The ranked research agenda in Section 8 identifies the welfare theory of biodiversity valuation as the most foundational priority. Without a welfare-theoretically grounded unit of account, biodiversity markets cannot aggregate, credits cannot be priced, the social cost of biodiversity loss cannot be estimated, and the private finance instruments that the GBF architecture requires cannot proceed on a sound economic foundation. The academic economics and finance community has made a strong start since 2023; what the field now needs is a deliberate research programme that addresses the theoretical foundations systematically, rather than proceeding as though they were already resolved.

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A. Architecture Data Sources

Data sources for Table 1: GEF Annual Report 2024; GBFF Council documents and press releases (thegef.org, June 2025); NatureFinance.info biodiversity commitment tracker (November 2024 update); CEPF impact report (cepf.net, 2025); GFCR portfolio data (2024); OECD CRS Rio Marker data (OECD.Stat, 2022 latest available); World Bank PROGREEN programme documentation; Amazon Fund Secretariat annual report 2024. All figures in USD at contemporaneous exchange rates.

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